

LAND TENURE DYNAMICS IN GEOGRAPHICALLY ISOLATED AND DISADVANTAGED COMMUNITY: INSIGHTS FROM MINDANAO, PHILIPPINES

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Abstract

A geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Areas (GIDAs), Barangay Kiorao is located in the Municipality of Kibawe, Province of Bukidnon, Mindanao, Philippines. The goal of this study is to assess land tenure rights in Kiorao. The objectives are as follows: 1) Determine the different land uses in the barangay, 2) Assess the natural resource development potential, 3) Determine the forms of land tenure arrangements in the community; and 4) Identify the key stakeholders in the land tenure arrangement. The methodology employed use of secondary land use data, participatory workshops and geographic information system (GIS). The results showed that Kiorao is an agricultural community with 44.5% of the land dedicated to crop production, tree cover likewise covers a significant area at 36.7%. The remaining natural forest is merely riparian, thus, natural resources development options will be confined to agricultural and silvicultural. Tax declaration is the form of land tenure amongst 98% of the households, while 0.5% possess a land title. A Community-based Forest Management Agreement (CBFMA) was granted, but the community has been drowned with bureaucratic and technical requirements, not being able to extract timber which they have planted. While struggling to make sense of the promised security, the community has to apply for renewal of the CBFMA, now clouded with a competing process of an ancestral domain claim. The concept of convergence among government program is much needed in this particular experience of Kiorao so that land tenure is secured for the community; settlers and indigenous peoples.

Keywords: GIDAs, Land Tenure Security, Land Use, Land Cover, Community Based Forest Management.

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines, with its remarkable biodiversity and intricate socio-political landscape, is home to Mindanao, the country's second-largest island. Mindanao is noted for its cultural diversity, ample natural resources, and a history marked by conflict and developmental delays (Madrigal, Cuesta, and Somerville 2024). Within the nation's framework for progress, "Ambisyon Natin 2040" (Our Vision) stands out as a blueprint for future growth. It represents the unified ambitions of the Filipino populace towards a future marked by economic prosperity, social inclusivity, and robust resilience (National Economic and Development Authority [NEDA], 2016). This vision propels the nation toward a future where poverty is eradicated, and quality of life is enhanced, ensuring sustainable development across generations. Serving as a fundamental reference, "Ambisyon Natin 2040" informs the strategic direction of the Philippine Development Plan (PDP), ensuring consistent policy development and strategic implementation across successive governmental terms (NEDA, 2016).

The PDP aims to materialize the aspirations of Ambisyon Natin 2040 by focusing on rapid economic growth, infrastructure enhancement, poverty eradication, and equitable opportunities for all Filipinos (NEDA, 2017). However, Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Areas (GIDAs) remain marginalized due to geographic isolation and socio-economic challenges. These areas, which are difficult to access due to rugged terrain, poor infrastructure, and vulnerability to conflict, face limited access to essential services such as healthcare, education, and land security (Mandac et al., 2023). Addressing development gaps in GIDAs is critical to ensuring inclusive growth, particularly in Mindanao, where many communities fall under this classification.

The Philippine Development Plan (PDP) 2023-2028 emphasizes a whole-of-society approach in modernizing agriculture and agribusiness to improve efficiency, market access, and resilience across the agricultural value chain (NEDA 2023). These initiatives align with the national goals of inclusive economic growth, poverty alleviation, and sustainable food systems in the Philippines.

A critical component of this transformation is land tenure security, which influences agricultural productivity, land governance, and environmental sustainability. In GIDAs, where many communities rely on subsistence farming, tenure security plays a vital role in economic stability and local development. The lack of secure land rights in these areas hinders investments, weakens land governance, and exacerbates poverty, making it imperative to implement context-sensitive land policies that cater to marginalized populations (Mandac et al., 2023).

Within the PDP, land tenure is identified as a pivotal factor shaping national development. Secure and equitable land tenure systems underpin agricultural innovation and productivity, essential to the PDP's agenda for modernization and food security (NEDA, 2017). Studies have shown that tenure security contributes to rural investment and economic stability, aligning with the overarching goals of poverty alleviation and sustainable development (World Bank, 2019). However, research on land tenure has yielded mixed findings regarding its impact on agricultural productivity and economic resilience, especially in marginalized and isolated areas.

Salmerón-Manzano and Manzano-Agugliaro (2023) conducted a bibliometric analysis of global research trends on land tenure and identified three key phases: early research (1950–1999) that emphasized socioeconomics and demography, a second phase (2000–2009) that focused on land rights and reforms, and a more recent phase (2010–2020) that shifted toward environmental concerns such as deforestation and climate change. Their findings indicate that land tenure research increasingly aligns with sustainable development goals, particularly those related to poverty reduction, inequality, and environmental sustainability.

Despite the recognition of land tenure's role in economic development, research has highlighted the challenges of land market efficiency and governance. Michler and Shively (2016) found that despite formal land titling under Philippine agrarian reform policies, land rental markets remain inefficient. While land ownership correlates with higher efficiency,

informal tenure agreements also provide sufficient security for investment, challenging the assumption that formal titles alone drive productivity gains. These findings suggest that broader agrarian reforms beyond land titling are needed to enhance land market efficiency and sustainability.

A related study by Van der Ploeg et al. (2016) examined tenure reforms in the Northern Sierra Madre, Philippines, focusing on the legalization of customary land rights for conservation. The study found that state-led tenure formalization often exacerbated tenure insecurity, failing to achieve conservation goals due to weak enforcement mechanisms and misaligned policies. This underscores the importance of integrating local governance structures into conservation and land tenure programs.

Mitchell et al. (2015) analyzed land tenure issues in Asia and the Pacific, identifying key concerns such as unequal land distribution, displacement from large-scale land acquisitions, and limited legal protections for Indigenous groups. Their research emphasized that climate change and natural disasters further exacerbate tenure insecurity, particularly in vulnerable communities. To address these challenges, they recommend strengthening land governance, securing women's land rights, and promoting pro-poor land policies.

Further research by Singirankabo and Ertsen (2020) explored the direct link between land registration and agricultural productivity, finding limited empirical support for the assumption that formal registration enhances productivity. Instead, in some cases, land registration disrupted customary land rights and increased tenure insecurity. Moreover, they highlighted the gender disparities in land registration, noting that women often face systemic barriers to land access, which in turn limits their participation in agricultural development. These findings call for context-specific land governance strategies rather than a one-size-fits-all approach to land registration and tenure reform.

Recognizing the importance of land tenure security, Central Mindanao University (CMU) has actively engaged in research and extension programs aimed at supporting rural communities. Through its involvement with Barangay Kiorao, CMU aims to address land tenure challenges, aligning its efforts with national and regional policy frameworks to contribute to socioeconomic stability and agricultural modernization.

The primary aim of this research is to conduct a systematic evaluation of land tenure rights in Barangay Kiorao. The specified scientific objectives are as follows:

- a) To categorize the land use typologies within Barangay Kiorao by analyzing spatial distributions and land use patterns.
- b) To quantify the potential for natural resource development, utilizing a metric-based assessment to gauge sustainable exploitation capabilities.
- c) To elucidate the spectrum of land tenure frameworks operational within the community, characterizing each by legal and customary legitimacy.
- d) To map the network of primary actors engaged in land tenure protocols, defining their respective roles and influence within the tenure system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted in Barangay Kiorao, located in the Municipality of Kibawe, Province of Bukidnon, Mindanao, Philippines (Figure 1). The methodological framework of this study is anchored in the principles of Rapid Participatory Research Approach, utilizing a range of tools and techniques to encapsulate the multi-dimensional aspects of human-land interactions. These interactions are pivotal for understanding the qualitative and quantitative dynamics of land use and livelihood, and how these elements correlate with land security.

Figure 1: Location Map of Barangay Kiorao

Figure 2 shows the Analytical and Methodological Framework adopted from Bruno, Aguinatan and Toledo-Bruno (2024) rooted in the Ambisyon Natin 2040 and operationalized by the Philippine Development Plan (PDP). The research directly responds to the national developmental agenda, intertwining with the local community's specific land tenure concerns. The research is designed using the Rapid Participatory Research Approach applying various tools and techniques. The research process, methods and tools includes the creation of a Barangay Working Group, preliminary landscape scanning, and participatory land use mapping.

Land Use Mapping and Livelihood Scanning

Human-Land interaction is central to the framework. Thus, community land use and livelihood is captured to understand if there are relations to the quality of people's interaction to the land security. The interactions between the residents and their land were dissected to understand their livelihood dependencies on land resources. Land tenure defines the relationship between people and land, influencing economic stability, social equity, and rural development. Secure tenure promotes investment and livelihoods, while insecurity leads to poverty and conflict, especially for marginalized groups. Recognizing customary rights and ensuring equitable access are key to sustainable development (FAO, 2002). Thus, it is important to understand how barangay Kiorao residents are using the land, more specifically in terms of livelihood. The data will reveal people's interaction with the land in terms of how they utilize it to support their daily needs.

The study used a 2018 land use/land cover map from the Environmental Science for Social Change (ESSC) as a baseline. Geographic Information System (GIS) technology was used to extract the land use/land cover specific for Barangay Kiorao. Although the map provided a starting point, field validation was paramount to identify and rectify data gaps, culminating in an updated and community-validated land use/land cover map.

Land Tenure Mapping and Analysis

The participatory approach extended to land tenure mapping and analysis. While government agencies such as the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) maintain land tenure maps, the complexity of formal and informal tenure arrangements necessitated a ground-level understanding. The process includes the following:

- Inventory of households: the team requested from the barangay secretary a list of households per settlement in the barangay;
- Focus Group Discussion: the team conducted an FGD participated by the representatives of the community aimed at: 1) Presenting and validating the inventory of households, 2) Inventory of different land tenure each household over their lands; 3) mapping out the spatial distribution of land and land ownership (tenure);

Stakeholder Analysis

The stakeholder and power relation analysis delved into the varying degrees of influence and interest of different stakeholders in the land tenure sphere. The use of Venn diagrams in participatory workshop facilitated this analysis, ensuring that community representatives were given a voice in the process. Thus, the following criteria was used in selecting the community representatives for the Focus Group Discussion (FGD):

- Barangay and Purok Officials
- Representatives from each settlement who are familiar of the households;
- Resource users/having strong interaction with the natural resources available in the community

Figure 2: Research Framework

While the effort is to include all the learned community members. It is acknowledged that some of them will not attend, or will not be able to attend in the FGD and other activities. Thus, Key Informant Interview (KII) was conducted specifically for the tribal leaders.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Land Use and Land Cover

The Table 2 shows the distribution of land use and cover in Barangay Kiorao. The most extensive category is agricultural land, which occupies 251.14 hectares, accounting for 44.5% of the total area. This indicates a significant emphasis on agriculture within the barangay. The second-largest category is “Other Tree Cover” with 207.13 hectares, making up 36.7% of the area, suggesting a substantial presence of non-forest trees, possibly including managed tree crops or agroforestry systems.

The “river” category is also notable, covering 52.96 hectares or 9.4% of the land, indicating the presence of considerable water bodies that might be significant for the local ecosystem and could play a role in irrigation. “Grassland” and “Built up Area” follow, with 5.6% and 1.2% respectively, suggesting limited urban development and presence of open grassy areas, possibly for grazing or as natural habitat. The least covered land types are “shrubland” and “natural forest”, at 1.8% and 0.7% respectively. The notably small area of natural forest may raise environmental concerns, indicating heavy loss of primary forest.

Table 1: Barangay Kiorao General Land Use/Cover

Land Use/Cover	Area (ha)	Percentage
Agricultural land	251.14	44.5 %
Other Tree Cover	207.13	36.7%
River	52.96	9.4%
Grassland	31.65	5.6%
Shrubland	10.41	1.8%
Built up Area	6.66	1.2%
Natural Forest	3.94	0.7%
Total	563.89	100%

The predominance of agricultural land emphasizes the importance of farming activities in Barangay Kiorao's economy and land-use planning. The large area under “Other Tree Cover” may complement agricultural production through the provision of fruit, nuts, or timber and could be indicative of diversified agricultural practices. However, it also reflect areas that are in transition or have been modified from their natural state. The proportion of land occupied by rivers suggests water is a significant feature in the landscape, which have implications for local biodiversity, recreation, and agriculture.

The minimal built-up are confirms the predominantly rural character of the barangay. The limited grassland and shrubland areas suggest these land covers are not a primary feature of the barangay’s landscape, which may limit certain types of wildlife or agricultural practices such as extensive livestock grazing.

The extremely low percentage of natural forest is a critical environmental finding, highlighting a potential area for conservation efforts. It raises questions about biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, and ecosystem services, all of which are important considerations for environmental sustainability and resilience against climate change. Nonetheless, it is important to note the presence of naturally growing tree species such as *Vitex parviflora*, *Shorea contorta*, *Pterocarpus indicus*, *Shore sp.*, *Ficus sp.*, *Trema orientalis*. Most of these species are extracted for lumber in the construction of houses. On the other hand, common planted tree species includes: *Gmelina arborea*, *falcataria*, *Leucaena leucocephala*, *Mangifera indica*, *Gliricidia sepium*. While these trees are mostly for timer, residents are prohibited to cut by DENR in the absence of approved Community Resources Management Framework Plan (CRMF) and Resource Utilization Plan (PUP). Another potential source of income, falcata, but aside from regulatory hurdles, current market price and linkage is a problem. Non-timber forest products are also available but are said to be limited given the limited forest in the community. Though limited, bamboo production is identified as a potential for development and can be an additional income if sustained with market linkages.

Table 3 provides the details of agricultural land uses in Barangay Kiorao. Corn is the dominant crop, occupying 90.13 hectares, which constitutes 35.89% of the total agricultural land. This is followed closely by rubber plantations that cover 81.05 hectares, amounting to 32.27% of the agricultural area. Rice paddies also make up a significant portion, covering 21.19 hectares and

comprising 8.44% of the land dedicated to agriculture. Coconut cultivation occupies 19.58 hectares or 7.80% of the agricultural land, suggesting a moderate presence of this crop in the local farming system. Corn grown under tree plantations takes up 4.92% of the agricultural land, with 12.35 hectares, potentially indicating some integration of cropping and forestry practices. Sugarcane is cultivated on 11.29 hectares (4.50%), while fruit crops (excluding mango and cassava, which are specified separately) cover 5.28 hectares, accounting for 2.10%. Oil palm and mango have smaller presences with 1.84% and 1.46% respectively. The least area is dedicated to cassava, at 0.62%, and to a mixed-use category combining cassava, mango, and corn, at just 0.16% over 0.41 hectares.

Table 2: Barangay Kiorao Agricultural Land Use/Cover

Land Use/Cover	Area (ha)	Percentage
Corn	90.13	35.89%
Rubber	81.05	32.27%
Rice	21.19	8.44%
Coconut	19.58	7.80%
Corn under tree plantations	12.35	4.92%
Sugarcane	11.29	4.50%
Fruit Crops	5.28	2.10%
Oil palm	4.62	1.84%
Mango	3.66	1.46%
Cassava	1.56	0.62%
Mixed: cassava, mango, corn	0.41	0.16%
Total	251.14	100%

The agricultural profile of Barangay Kiorao suggests a strong focus on crop cultivation, with corn and rubber as the most extensively farmed crops. The significant area devoted to these crops could be due to their economic viability, local soil and climate conditions, and market demand.

The emphasis on these two crops also implies a reliance on them for economic stability, which could be a risk if there is market volatility or crop failure due to pests, diseases, or climate events. The extent of rice cultivation is noteworthy given its staple food status in many cultures, indicating its importance to local food security and dietary preferences. The presence of coconut cultivation aligns with traditional uses and market demand for coconut products, which may be significant in the region.

The mixed cropping system observed with corn under tree plantations suggests an awareness of sustainable agricultural practices. However, the relatively small scale of this practice indicates that it may not be widely adopted or may be in an experimental or developmental phase. The low percentages of land devoted to sugarcane, fruit crops, oil palm, and mango may indicate either limited market opportunities for these crops, challenging growing conditions, or both. The very small area for cassava and the mixed cropping suggests that these are not main agricultural products or that they are grown mainly for subsistence or small-scale local trade.

Figure 3: Land Use/Cover of Barangay Kiorao

Considering the dominance of monoculture crops like corn and rubber, issues related to soil degradation, pesticide use, and vulnerability to pests is a challenge. Diversification of crops could be beneficial to mitigate such risks and ensure long-term agricultural sustainability. The data implies that Barangay Kiorao’s agricultural land use is characterized by a few predominant crops, which have economic benefits but also presents challenges for sustainability and resilience. This calls for a balanced approach in agricultural planning, potentially incorporating more diversified and integrated farming systems to safeguard against economic and environmental risks. Barangay Kiorao was surrounded by two major rivers: Muleta and Lagasan Rivers. These rivers are the traditional fishing grounds of Manobo. Currently, they

have two spring: Purok 2 Barrel Spring and Purok 6 Spring, which are sources for drinking, laundry, and part of livelihood. While these are privately owned, these are open to the public. Physical access is a concern especially during the rainy season as horses is the mode of transportation in hauling water. To solve this problem, the barangay constructed a water distribution line.

Land Tenure Assessment

Land remains a primary source of livelihood in many developing countries like the Philippines. As discussed in the preceding sections, around 85.2% of the lands in Kiorao is used either for agricultural or agroforestry purposes. Land is a source of food, shelter, income and social identity (Liversage (2015)). Access to land reduces the vulnerability of people to hunger and poverty. On the other hand, absence of land tenure security will exclude people in participating development programs. Where programs or services are available, absence of secured land tenure discourages people to take long-term investment. Velasco et.al (2014) citing Alston and Mueller (2005) put forward that denying the poor with property rights creates difficulty among household in terms of participating formal economic activities resulting in a development that excludes those most in need.

Community Land Tenure in Kiorao

Lands in the Philippines are legally and technically classified into two: 1) alienable and disposal (A and D), 2) forest lands. In Barangay Kiorao people classify land tenure as: 1) titled, 2) tax declaration, 3) tenants. Technically, those with tax declarations can either fall within the A and D or forestlands. For the purpose of the study, community classification is also factored. Based on the list from the Barangay Secretary a total of 206 households are considered residents in the barangay. Table 3 shows the tenurial status by household, while Figure 4 shows the spatial distribution in terms of tenure. The participatory workshop revealed that 99.5% of the households only possess a tax declaration as a form of tenurial security. This is understandable because the area falls within the forestland classification. However, the same workshop also revealed one household possessing a land title, a more secure form of tenure. Meanwhile, there are 4 households representing 2% which are tenant, these households are those with tax declaration lands. In terms of area, 90% is covered only with tax declaration, while 1% with a title. The remaining percentage are the bodies of water (river/creeks).

Table 4 provides an overview of land tenure in Barangay Kiorao, categorized by tenure type and ownership in terms of area (hectares). Tax Declaration is the predominant tenure form, comprising 498.73 hectares and accounting for 88.45% of the land under the owner-tiller category, while Tenant ownership represents only 1.36%. Titled land amounts to a mere 4.52 hectares, less than 1% of the total, and there is no tenant ownership. Water bodies cover 52.96 hectares, which is 9.39% of the owner-tiller's land and contribute to the same percentage of the total land area. The overall tenure shows that 98.64% of the land is under the owner-tiller category and a small fraction of 1.36% under tenants, totaling 563.89 hectares. This indicates a vast majority of the land is controlled by owner-tillers, with very little held by tenants, and that the water bodies form a significant part of the landscape.

Table 3: Tenurial Status by Households

Tenure	Nature of Ownership				Total	
	Owner-tiller	Percentage	Tenant	Percentage		
Tax Declaration	498.73	88.45%	7.68	1.36%	506.41	90%
Titled	4.52	0.80%	-	-	4.52	1%
Water body	52.96	9.39%			52.96	9%
Total	556.20	98.64%	7.68	1.36%	563.89	100%

Figure 4: Land Tenure Map of Barangay Kiorao

Table 4: Tenurial Status by Area (hectares)

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Community-Based Forest Management Agreement (CBFMA)

The government, through the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), addressed concerns over land tenure security as early as 1999 by initiating the Community-Based Forest Management Agreement (CBFMA) Program. This production-sharing agreement, established by DENR Administrative Order No. 96-29, involves a 25-year partnership, renewable for another 25 years, between the DENR and participating community organizations. In Barangay Kiorao, residents formed the Kiorao Upland Farmers Association (KUFA), a people’s organization registered with the Securities and Exchange Commission, to engage in the CBFMA program. KUFA was granted a CBFMA in 1999, which is set to expire in 2024 and encompasses 544.18 hectares. While the impact of the CBFMA on KUFA members is beyond the scope of this study, focus group discussions have indicated widespread implementation bottlenecks in the CBFMA program, a trend not exclusive to Barangay Kiorao but apparent across the program's broader execution.

Pulhin, Peras, Tapia (2013) noted that the government through the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) have gained more from the Community-Based Forest Management (CBFM) program than the intended local beneficiaries. Despite the DENR's mandate to promote sustainable resource development, the benefits have skewed more towards the government in many CBFM areas. The land cover in the area supports the assertion that community members have been proactive in planting trees for fruit and timber, including species such as falcata, mahogany, and gmelina. This reflects environmental considerations and an economic incentive, as there is an expectation to harvest and profit from the trees planted. However, to date, KUFA has not received harvesting permits due to unmet technical requirements, such as developing a Community Resource Management Framework Plan (CRMF) and a resource utilization plan. Consequently, there have been reports of illegal tree felling in the area. The bureaucratic and technical hurdles hindering the CBFMA have been further compounded by issues in organizational management in recent years. This has led to a decline in member participation and difficulties in convening meetings. Although the barangay council reports being uninformed of KUFA's activities, the president of the organization insists that regular meetings are held and that they maintain a collaborative relationship with the DENR.

The Kiorao CBFM situation has long been highlighted by Pulhin, Peras, and Tapia (2013) where bureaucratic inefficiencies, restrictive regulations, and socio-political barriers limited its success. Despite policies granting tenure rights to local communities, multi-tiered governance and delayed permit processing hinder effective implementation. Institutional reforms are

needed to create an enabling environment that fosters sustainability and equitable benefit-sharing. Despite differing accounts, it is evident that the goal of land tenure security through CBFMA has yet to be realized in Barangay Kiorao. The looming expiry of the agreement in 2024 adds to the complexity, as KUFA faces an impending evaluation for renewal. However, the assessment should not be limited to the organization; it should also encompass the program itself and its implementation by the DENR. Additionally, the intricacies of the Indigenous Peoples Rights Act (IPRA) introduce another layer of complexity to the situation.

Ancestral Domain Claim

In many highland regions of Bukidnon such as Kiorao, indigenous communities like the Manobo are recognized under the Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act (IPRA), which grants them rights to claim ancestral domains. Nonetheless, IPRA also safeguards existing property rights as articulated in Section 56: "Property rights within the ancestral domains already existing and/or vested upon the effectiveness of this Act, shall be recognized and respected," hence recognizing Community-Based Forest Management Agreements (CBFMA) as pre-existing rights. The impending expiration of the CBFMA in 2024 brings about a legal dilemma, as Section 59 of IPRA prohibits government agencies from granting new concessions while applications for Certificate of Ancestral Domain Title (CADT) are under consideration.

Despite the absence of official communication in Barangay Kiorao about claims on ancestral domains, reports suggest that Manobo leaders have initiated claims that encompass areas within the Municipality of Kibawe, including Kiorao. This poses a contentious issue in territories presently occupied by migrant settlers, bringing to the forefront the question of land tenure security. While IPRA aims to redress historical injustices faced by indigenous populations, it must also deliver justice to migrant settlers who lawfully acquired land, adhering to the due process of their time.

Stakeholders in the Land Tenure in the community

The Venn diagram (Figure 5) reflects the complex network of stakeholders involved in the land tenure dynamics of Barangay Kiorao, through a simple stakeholder analysis using two variables: interest and influence. By interest, meaning the level of impact it has on one's life in terms the land, while influence refers to the level of decision-making that could affect the land. The bigger the circle the bigger the interest, while distance from center means lesser influence. Analysis is carried out through a participatory process. The overlapping circles illustrate the interconnections and potential for collaborative or conflicting interests among groups which includes the following:

- **Landowners:** By staking a claim over a land, means that the person has an interest over the property. Participants noted that landowners have the highest interest when lands are involved;
- **Kiorao Upland Farmers Association:** Legally, until 2024 the farmers of Barangay Kiorao has a tenure through a CBFMA being a member of KUFA which received the tenure in behalf of the community.

- **Barangay and Municipal Officials:** Meanwhile, any transfer, agreements or any arrangements pertaining to land or involving land conflicts will have to pass through the Barangay Council. Thus, Barangay Official are the next group who has interest over land issues. This is beside the local tax that can be generated out of the transaction;
- **National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP):** A government agency mandated to process ancestral domain/land titles to indigenous peoples;
- **Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR):** A government agency responsible for governing and supervising the exploration, development, utilization, and conservation of the country's natural resources, including land.
- **Tribal Leaders:** On the other hand, particularly in the rural communities, tribal leaders has strong interest on lands.
- **Department of Agrarian Reform (DAR):** A government agency responsible for the redistribution of agrarian land in the Philippines.

The central area where most circles overlap represents common ground where the interests of all stakeholders converge. Notably, the Municipal Government, Barangay Officials, and tribal leaders share a significant overlap, indicating close collaboration or shared jurisdiction. The tenants and DAR, along with the NCIP and landowners, have their specific circles, suggesting distinct roles or interests within the tenure system. The diagram underscores the need for coordinated efforts and inclusive dialogue among all parties to address tenure security, land use, and development while respecting indigenous rights and promoting social equity. Each stakeholder's unique position and influence in this network are critical to the governance and management of land resources in Barangay Kiorao.

Figure 5: Stakeholder Analysis

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The study revealed that Barangay Kiorao has leveraged its diverse agricultural practices as the backbone of the community's economy, reflecting investment and interest in land development. The CBFMA, while intended to enhance land tenure security, has encountered significant challenges, leaving the community at a crossroads as it approaches the agreement's expiration and contends with competing ancestral domain claims.

The recommendation is to foster a synergistic approach involving all stakeholders to address the multifaceted land tenure issues. The research suggests the potential for more productive land use through agroforestry and silviculture, driven by both economic and environmental incentives. It highlights the critical role of technical and organizational support from academic institutions, which could bridge existing gaps and contribute to the community's sustainable development.

Further, the research calls for a strengthened national dialogue, particularly regarding the implementation of IPRA in the face of CBFMA and the interests of small farmers. It emphasizes the need for harmonizing policies across government agencies to prevent exacerbating existing tensions and ensure equitable land tenure security. This convergence is vital to prevent setbacks into cycles of poverty and conflict, which the land tenure security programs aim to resolve.

The study recommends continued dialogue and coordination between government agencies, particularly the NCIP, to ensure the effective implementation of IPRA without compromising the rights of small farmers. It also points out the importance of academic institutions in providing much-needed technical assistance to address land tenure challenges.

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Declaration of Interest

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References

- 1) Brizzi and Liversage, H. (2015). Land tenure security and poverty reduction. Accessed through <https://www.ifad.org/en/web/knowledge/publication/asset/39397937> on 26 May 2020.
- 2) Bruno, E. N. Land Tenure Rights in a Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Community in Bukidnon, Philippines. <https://seybold-report.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Eric.pdf>
- 3) Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). (2002). *Land tenure and rural development*. FAO Land Tenure Studies. <https://www.fao.org/4/y4307e/y4307e00.pdf>

- 4) Livingsage, H. (2015). Land Tenure Security and Poverty Reduction. Accessed through <https://www.ifad.org/en/web/knowledge/publication/asset/39397937> on 26 May 2020.
- 5) Madrigal, L., Cuesta, J., & Somerville, S. (2024). *Indigenous Peoples, Land and Conflict in Mindanao, Philippines*. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper 10700. <https://doi.org/10.60572/q1e5-s577>
- 6) Mandac, R. G. C., Unipa, J. M. I., Fontanilla, R. C., Florentino, J. B., & Paracad, N. A. B. (2023). *Department of Health Programs: The Perspective of a Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Area of Peñablanca, Cagayan*. *International Multi-Disciplinary Research Journal*, 1(3). <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9751-2430>
- 7) Mbudzya, J. J., Gido, E. O., & Owuor, G. (2023). Determinants of land tenure security among small-holder farmers in rural Kenya: An ordered probit analysis. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 9(1), 2220232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2023.2220232>
- 8) Mindanao Daily (2019). Region 10 adopts convergence areas for peace and development to operationalize EO 70. Accessed on 9 June 2020 at <https://www.mindanaodailynews.com/news/the-region/cagayan-de-oro/region-10-adopts-convergence-areas-for-peace-and-development-tooperationalize-eo-70/>
- 9) National Economic and Development Authority. (2017). Philippine Development Plan 2017-2022. Retrieved from <https://www.neda.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/PDP-2017-2022-07-20-2017.pdf>
- 10) National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA). (2023). *Philippine Development Plan 2023-2028*. <https://www.neda.gov.ph>.
- 11) National Economic and Development Authority. (2016). Ambisyon Natin 2040: A Long-Term Vision for the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.neda.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Ambisyon-Natin-2040-Executive-Brief.pdf>
- 12) National Economic Development Authority-X (2019). RDC NorMin moves to operationalize EO 70 through CAPDev. <https://nro10.neda.gov.ph/rdc-normin-moves-to-operationalize-eo-70-through-capdev/>
- 13) Norton, R. D. (2014). Policy frameworks for international agricultural and rural development. *Encycl. Agric. Food Syst.*, 489-503. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-52512-3.00123-6>
- 14) Pulhin, J. M., Peras, R. J. J., & Tapia, M. A. (2013). *Forest Policies and Governance on an Uneven Playing Field: Barriers for a Successful CBFM in the Philippines*. In M. Inoue & G. Shivakoti (Eds.), *Multi-level forest governance in Asia: Recognizing diversity* (pp. xx-xx).
- 15) Republic of the Philippines. (2018). Executive Order No. 70, s. 2018. Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2018/12dec/20181204-EO-70-RRD.pdf>
- 16) Robin, T. A., Khan, M. A., Kabir, N., Rahaman, S. T., Karim, A., Mannan, I. I., ... & Rashid, I. (2019). Using spatial analysis and GIS to improve planning and resource allocation in a rural district of Bangladesh. *BMJ Global Health*, 4(Suppl 5), e000832. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2018-000832>
- 17) Valkonen, A. (2021). Examining sources of land tenure (in) security. A focus on authority relations, state politics, social dynamics and belonging. *Land Use Policy*, 101, 105191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.105191>
- 18) Velasco, M.A., Regadio, C.Q., Girado, M. B. (2014). Security of Tenure, Capital Accumulation and Quality of Life for Poverty Alleviation. *Social Development*
- 19) World Bank. (2019). The World Bank in the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/philippines/overview/>